
ORGANIZATIONAL JUSTICE AND JOB SATISFACTION FOR GENERAL EDUCATION TEACHERS IN SULTANATE OF OMAN

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Abstract:

Teacher is considered as one of the most important bases upon which the educational system is based because he assumes the responsibility of preparing young children to be good citizens in the future, bringing them up on good manners and teaching them moral and noble values. So, the authorities concerned in the ministry of Education, in general and managers or head masters at schools in particular, must give due cares to create a more healthy atmosphere favorable to teachers while working at schools. This objective can be achieved through the principle of treating all teachers equally without discrimination and such treatment must be based upon justice. Moreover, they also must spare no effort to develop good working relation between them and the teachers from one hand and teachers with each other from the other hand.

Keywords: Organizational; General Education; Job Satisfaction; Sultanate.

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1. Introduction

This stems from the fact that the realization of teachers of the importance of organizational justice, plays an essential role in raising their morale and developing a sense of belongingness in them, and this in turn helps much in raising their job performance level and to contribute more actively in achieving the intended goals from the education process.

The Organizational justice is considered as one of the most important subjects that draws the attention of most people working in the field of management, and this increasing attention is reflected in the great number of studies and researches conducted in relation to the organizational behavior and the development of human resources in organizations and creating organizational culture more suitable for social human and administrative purposes.

2. The Study's Problem and Questions

In spite of the great efforts exerted by the ministry of education to solve the problems faced by teachers through conducting training courses and implementing educational rehabilitation programs, which aims at developing the skills and abilities of teachers, but the wide and clear differences between the leadership styles adopted by manager and headmasters of general educational schools in sultanate of Oman, have left direct and negative effect on the level of the organizational justice and job satisfaction for teachers. Therefore, we restrict our choice of the study's problem to filed study conducted at the general educational schools in Sultanate of Oman. It is a fact confirmed beyond the slightest doubt that the realization of teachers that their managers and headmasters treat them justly has a direct bearing on their job satisfaction and this in turn reflect positively on their work performance, accordingly the studies problems can be identified as how far teachers at the general educational schools in the Sultanate of Oman realized the relation between organizational justice and job satisfaction. This can be done through finding answer for the following questions:

- 1) What are the theoretical basis upon which the relation between organizational justice and job satisfaction of teachers is built?
- 2) How fare teachers at general educational schools in sultanate of Oman realized organizational justice done by their managers and headmasters?
- 3) How fare teachers at general educational schools in sultanate of Oman, have job satisfaction?
- 4) Is there a statistically significant relation at ($\alpha = 0.05$) level between the organizational justice (interaction procedural and distributional) and job satisfaction dimensions for most teachers at the general educational schools in the sultanate of Oman?
- 5) Is there a statistically significant differences at ($\alpha = 0.05$) level in the degree at which teacher at general educational school in the sultanate of Oman realize educational organization justice done by their managers and headmasters and such differences attributed to variables such as social status, scientific qualifications, experiences and gender?
- 6) Is there a statistically significant differences at ($\alpha = 0.05$) level in the degree of job satisfaction felt by teachers of general educational schools in the sultanate of Oman and such differences attributed to variables such as social status, scientific qualifications, experiences and gender?
- 7) What is the plan proposed to achieve organizational justice at schools and improve job satisfaction for teacher in the general school in general education in sultanate of Oman?

3. The Study's Objectives

The main objective of this study is to identify the extent to which teacher in general educational school in sultanate of Oman realize organizational justice and its relation with job satisfaction. These main objectives can be subdivided into the following secondary questions?

- 1) To understand the concept of organizational justice with its deferent dimensions (interaction procedural and distributional).
- 2) To discover the relation between organizational justice with its deferent dimensions (interaction procedural and distributional) and job satisfaction for teachers at general educational schools in the sultanate of Oman.

- 3) To reach a proposed plan about how to achieve the relation between the two variables in such a manner that contributes to the improvement of teaching performance.

4. The Tools Used in the Study

The tools used in the study can be divided into two main tools:

- 1) Using a organizational justice measure developed by Niehoff & Moorman, 1993. which consists of 20 items used to measure interaction justice procedural justice and distributional justice. Such measure has been modified to suit with the research environment.
- 2) Developing a test to measure job satisfaction through referring back to several tools used by previous studies closely relevant to job satisfaction.

5. The Study's Methods

This study depend upon the descriptive methods through conducting a previous theoretical survey to construct the theoretical framework of the study, as well as field observation to gather data by using study's tools and the statistical analysis of such data in order to answer the questions raised by the study.

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